

D1.4

LogFrame
Methodology
Progress Report

D1.4	LogFrame Methodology Progress Report
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Disclaimer

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Abbreviations

AHP	Analytic Hierarchy Process
AP	Action Plan
BIOEAST	Central and Eastern European Initiative for Knowledge-based Agriculture, Aquaculture and Forestry in the Bioeconomy
CA	Consortium Agreement
CEE	Central and Eastern Europe
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
EBU	Bioeconomy University
EU	European Union
ExCom	Executive Committee
GA	Grant Agreement
ICA-CoP	European Community of Practice on Bioeconomy Education
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LFA	Logical Framework Approach
MS	Member States
NMG	National Mirror Group
OIC	Open Innovation Challenge
ÖMKi	Hungarian Research Institute of Organic Agriculture
PO	Project Officer
RDI	Research Development and Innovation
SIE	Sustainable Innovations Europe
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
ToR	Terms of Reference
TWG	Thematic Working Group
UniNet	Network of the bioeconomy universities from the Central and Eastern Europe
WP	Work Package

Introduction to the project

BOOST4BIOEAST is a Coordination and Support Action funded by the European Commission developed to support the BIOEAST Initiative with the aim of empowering national stakeholders in the Central Eastern European and Baltic countries for the development of national bioeconomy action plans and to build long-lasting structures and spaces of dialogue for national and macro-regional cooperation. The project will enrich knowledge on bioeconomy and stimulate related research and innovation across the macro-region.

Executive Summary

This deliverable (*D1.4 – LogFrame Methodology Progress Report*) presents the first comprehensive evaluation of how the Logical Framework Approach (LFA) has been applied within the BOOST4BIOEAST project to support structured planning, monitoring, and adaptive management across its eight Work Packages (WPs). The report assesses the coherence of the Logical Framework Matrices (Logframe Matrix) with the objectives defined in the Grant Agreement (GA), identifies gaps, misalignments and formulates recommendations to enhance the use of the LFA as a living management tool.

The LFA has served so far as a key instrument for ensuring consistency between strategic objectives and operational activities. It has enabled a harmonised, transparent, and comparable monitoring system that links long-term goals with expected outcomes and measurable outputs. The Coordination led by ÖMKi (Hungarian Research Institute of Organic Agriculture) and the active involvement of all WP Leaders have contributed to establishing a common methodology and shared understanding of the project logic across the consortium.

All WPs have prepared their Logframe Matrix in alignment with the GA, demonstrating a clear logical connection between project goals, outcomes, and deliverables. The LFA has proven particularly valuable in promoting coherence, accountability, and cross-WP comparability. However, several challenges were identified, including incomplete or superficial input from some WP Leaders, irregular updates of the matrices, and inconsistent use of indicators. Occasional confusion between goals, outcomes, and outputs was also observed, alongside insufficiently defined risks and assumptions.

To address these challenges, the report recommends strengthening methodological support, providing regular follow-up sessions for WP Leaders, and supporting the better integration of Logframe Matrix reviews into the project's regular management cycle. Improved understanding and consistent application of the LFA will help ensure that it functions not merely as a reporting requirement but as a dynamic instrument for learning, coordination, and adaptive management.

Overall, the LFA has significantly contributed to enhancing the project's internal coherence, transparency, and alignment with the BIOEAST Initiative's strategic objectives. With continuous refinement and active engagement of WP Leaders, the Logframe Matrix will remain a central tool for progress monitoring until the end of the project.

1 Introduction

The BOOST4BIOEAST project, supporting the BIOEAST Initiative, aims to strengthen the transition toward sustainable and circular bioeconomy across the Central and Eastern European (CEE) macro-region. The project's activities are designed to operationalise the BIOEAST Vision (BIOEAST, 2018) through an integrated, multi-level approach that connects macro-regional coordination with national and thematic implementation. Within this framework, the LFA provides a common structure for aligning strategic objectives, monitoring implementation, and ensuring coherence across the eight WPs, seven Thematic Working Groups (TWGs), and eleven national BIOEAST Bioeconomy HUBs (HUBs).

The LFA has been widely applied by international organisations and the European Commission (EC) as a structured planning and management tool. It links long-term goals with expected outcomes, outputs, and concrete activities through a transparent cause-and-effect logic. In BOOST4BIOEAST, the LFA serves not only as a management instrument but also as a participatory learning framework that supports reflection, accountability, and adaptive management. By encouraging annual updates, the approach ensures that project actions remain responsive to evolving policy contexts, stakeholder needs, and emerging opportunities in the bioeconomy.

To facilitate harmonisation, a dedicated Logframe Matrix guideline and common templates were developed and shared with all WP, TWG, and HUB Coordinators. These provided the conceptual and operational basis for preparing their individual Logframe Matrices. Each matrix defines the goal hierarchy, indicators, and underlying assumptions, complemented by detailed activity plans. This deliverable only assessing the WPs' Logframe matrices as the evaluation of TWG and HUB Logframe matrices will be part of a separate deliverable (*D6.4 – HUB and TWG Evaluation Report*). The Logframe Matrix development process was coordinated by ÖMKi and followed a participatory approach involving all WP and Task Leaders, ensuring that the Logframe Matrices accurately reflect the interconnected nature of BOOST4BIOEAST's objectives and tasks.

The first complete set of Logframe Matrices was finalised by May 2024 and reviewed between December 2024 and January 2025, establishing a harmonised monitoring baseline across the project. This process culminated in the first macro-regional reflection session held during the Annual Meeting in April 2025, forming the basis of the present report.

This deliverable documents the development and implementation of the WPs' LFA across the BOOST4BIOEAST project, assessing its contribution to improving coherence, transparency, and learning among partners. It provides a comparative analysis of the Logframe Matrices across all eight WPs, identifying key challenges, and areas for methodological improvement. The deliverable first introduces the LFA in Chapter 2, outlining its theoretical foundations, the specific structure applied in the project, the process through which the Logframe Matrices were

developed, and the analytical framework used for assessment. Chapter 3 then analyses how stakeholders are involved throughout the WPs, describing the types of stakeholders engaged and comparing the communication channels used across WPs. Chapter 4 offers an assessment of the Goals, Outcomes, and Outputs, including an examination of gaps and misalignments from the GA, as well as feedback from partners and project coordination on the functioning of the LFA. At the end, Chapter 5 summarises the lessons learned from the first project period and offers guidance for future updates and adaptive management.

By consolidating these experiences, the report contributes to building a shared understanding of monitoring practices within the BIOEAST community and supports evidence-based decision-making at both national and macro-regional levels. It thereby strengthens the role of the project partners in jointly steering the bioeconomy transition across the BIOEAST region in line with the strategic objectives of the BIOEAST Initiative. This report provides both an overview of the BOOST4BIOEAST LFA and a mid-term evaluation of its progress. It will be further revised and expanded in a final report (*D1.5 - LogFrame Methodology Second Progress Report*), which will be submitted at the end of the project.

2 Logical Framework Approach

2.1 Logical Framework Approach in theory

The LFA is a project planning and management tool widely adopted by international organisations as well as the EC. It helps establish a clear hierarchy between the overall objectives and the activities required to achieve them, enabling continuous monitoring of the project and verification of interim results during implementation (EC, 2025). The Logframe Matrix is the tool and outcome of applying the LFA: it summarises the ideas and structure developed throughout the process. The resulting Logframe Matrix provides a concise, standardised, and easily comprehensible common language for all project participants, facilitating communication and coordination among stakeholders (Örtengren, 2004).

Steps of the Method

A high-quality and valuable Logframe Matrix is one that provides a clear and logical summary of the project for all participants, decision-makers, and funders. To achieve this, it is essential to involve all relevant stakeholders in the planning process and to develop the project idea collaboratively (Sida Civil Society Centreer, 2006).

Before moving on to the detailed design of the project, a thorough situation analysis must be conducted to gather as much information as possible. It is also crucial to evaluate whether the chosen objective is realistically achievable, considering long-term sustainability and the availability of necessary resources (human, financial, material, etc.).

Therefore, the Logframe Matrix consists of two main phases (NORAD, 1999):

1. Analysis phase: conducting a detailed situation analysis to identify problems, stakeholders, objectives, and possible strategies;
2. Planning phase: once sufficient information has been gathered, the actual Logframe Matrix is developed, summarising the project's structure, objectives, indicators, and assumptions.

Figure 1. Phases of the LFA (Ministry of Economic Affairs, 2010)

I. Analysis phase

The analysis phase of the LFA consists of three main steps:

Step 1: Stakeholder analysis

Stakeholder analysis can be a complex and time-consuming process, as it is often difficult to identify all individuals or organisations that may benefit from or be negatively affected by the project. In many cases, the project's scope turns out to extend well beyond the original assumptions, influencing actors who were not initially considered. The goal of this step is to map all relevant stakeholders and understand their interests, influence, and potential roles in the project (Sida Civil Society Center, 2006).

Step 2: Problem analysis

This step focuses on identifying the main problems and defining their cause-and-effect relationships, which are best visualised through a problem tree. After completing the stakeholder analysis, the current situation is examined based on the gathered information. The central problem (the focal problem) is selected, and the related issues are arranged around it to reveal logical connections. In the problem tree, the causes of the focal problem are placed

below it, while the effects appear above. The leaves of the tree represent specific issues whose elimination will ultimately address the focal problem and thus lead to achieving the project's objectives (NORAD, 1999).

Step 3: Objective analysis

Based on the identified problems, objectives are defined and means-ends relationships are established. The problem tree is transformed into an objective tree, where each problem is reformulated into a corresponding positive statement or goal. Consequently, the objective tree represents the mirror image of the problem tree: cause-and-effect relationships are converted into means-and-ends relationships. Solving a specific problem therefore means achieving the corresponding objective, which contributes to reaching the overall goal of the project (AusAID, 2005).

II. Planning phase

The planning phase of the LFA can be divided into four main steps:

1. Defining the project logic;
2. Formulating assumptions;
3. Identifying indicators;
4. Preparing the budget.

Completing these four steps, the Logframe Matrix summarises the project's key components, the corresponding measurable indicators, their sources of verification, and the external factors that may significantly influence the project's success. In its standard format, the Logframe Matrix consists of four rows (Goal, Outcome, Output and Activities) and four columns (Summary, Indicators, Means of Verification, Risk/Assumptions). The planning phase determines what will be entered into each cell of this matrix (EC, 2025).

Step 1: Defining the project logic

The aim of this step is to select the most suitable strategy through the analysis of alternatives and define the measurable objectives and the activities leading to them based on the objective tree, and the logical connections between them are verified.

These elements are placed in the first column of the Logframe Matrix (NORAD, 1999):

- The first row contains the overall (strategic) goal, representing the long-term benefits and impact that justify the project's implementation.
- The second row specifies the project outcome, a short-term, tangible purpose achieved once all project activities are successfully completed.
- The third row lists the expected results (outputs), the direct deliverables of the project that must be achieved and maintained to fulfil the project purpose.

Activity Description	Indicators	Means of Verification	Assumptions
Goal or Impact – The long term development impact (policy goal) that the activity contributes at a national or sectoral level	How the achievement will be measured – including appropriate targets (quantity, quality and time)	Sources of information on the Goal indicator(s) – including who will collect it and how often	
Purpose or Outcome – The medium term result(s) that the activity aims to achieve – in terms of benefits to target groups	How the achievement of the Purpose will be measured – including appropriate targets (quantity, quality and time)	Sources of information on the Purpose indicator(s) – including who will collect it and how often	Assumptions concerning the Purpose to Goal linkage
Component Objectives or Intermediate Results – This level in the objectives or results hierarchy can be used to provide a clear link between outputs and outcomes (particularly for larger multi-component activities)	How the achievement of the Component Objectives will be measured – including appropriate targets (quantity, quality and time)	Sources of information on the Component Objectives indicator(s) – including who will collect it and how often	Assumptions concerning the Component Objective to Output linkage
Outputs – The tangible products or services that the activity will deliver	How the achievement of the Outputs will be measured – including appropriate targets (quantity, quality and time)	Sources of information on the Output indicator(s) – including who will collect it and how often	Assumptions concerning the Output to Component Objective linkage

Figure 2. General structure and content of a Logframe Matrix (AusAID, 2005)

Step 2: Identifying indicators and sources of verification

Up to this point, the qualitative aspects of the project - such as the quantity, quality, and timing of activities, resources, and goals - have not been specified. These are quantified through indicators, which provide objective and measurable evidence of progress. Each indicator must reflect the essential changes the project seeks to achieve (not side effects), report facts, not opinions, and ideally refer to only one specific objective. A good indicator meets the SMART criteria: Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Realistic, and Time-based (Örtengren, 2004).

Indicators are entered into the second column of the Logframe Matrix, while their corresponding sources and means of verification are listed in the third column. These two columns are completed together, pairing each indicator with its verification method or data source (Sida Civil Society Center, 2006).

Step 3: Formulating assumptions

Successful project outcomes depend not only on internal activities but also on external conditions beyond the project's direct control. These assumptions are recorded in the fourth column of the Logframe Matrix and represent factors that must hold true for the project to succeed. When filling this column, the process moves from bottom to top. At the base are the preconditions, which must be met before the project can start. Moving upward, we define the assumptions that must be fulfilled for activities (inputs) to produce the expected outputs. At the next level, we identify the assumptions linking outputs to the project purpose. Finally, at the top, we specify the assumptions that, together with the project purpose, must be achieved for the overall objectives to be realized (Middleton, 2005).

Step 4: Preparing the budget

The final step involves preparing the project budget, assessing the required and available resources - both financial and non-financial - to ensure feasibility and sustainability. This step is not necessarily part of the Logframe Matrix and can be listed separately (NORAD, 1999).

Overall, project planning is rarely a one-person task. Therefore, it is strongly recommended to organise workshops throughout both the analysis and planning phases. Collaborative discussions help ensure that all relevant perspectives are included and that the resulting Logframe Matrix accurately reflects a shared understanding of the project's goals and implementation logic.

2.2 Structure of the BOOST4BIOEAST Logical Framework Approach

In the BOOST4BIOEAST project, the LFA provides all WPs, TWGs, and HUBs with a common framework to systematically monitor the progress of their activities in alignment with their goals from the start until the end of the project. Logframe Matrices have been developed early on during implementation and are updated throughout the project lifetime. By revising these matrices annually as internal activity plans, the LFA supports both the overall project and each WP, TWG and HUB in a structured and transparent monitoring process.

The introduction of the LFA aims to:

- provide clear roadmaps (internal activity plans) for WPs, TWGs, and HUBs on a yearly basis that specify planned activities with timelines and responsible partners;
- ensure the existence of a coherent monitoring framework across the entire project duration which regularly informs project-level decision-making and action planning resulting in better adaptiveness to changes and modifications;
- encourage participants to reflect on how planned activities lead to outputs, how outputs contribute to outcomes, and how these collectively support the long-term goal;
- underpin this logical structure with objectively measurable indicators and clear sources of verification.

For the WPs, the Logframe Matrices are developed through four main steps:

1. Stakeholder analysis - this step was optional for WP leads;
2. Stakeholder list;
3. Logframe matrix;
4. Activities.

For the HUBs and TWGs, the process is extended with a fifth step, the development of a Problem Tree. This tool enables HUB and TWG members to jointly identify and structure the core elements of their Logframe Matrix.

In contrast, this step was not required for the WPs, as the GA already provides a clear definition of the main problems and the objectives set to address them within each WP, therefore, this deliverable does not address that aspect.

Step 1: Stakeholder analyses

The stakeholder analysis examines the actors (stakeholders) involved in the project and their respective roles, interests, and influence. Each stakeholder group is assessed according to the following criteria:

- Interest in the project;
- Influence;
- Engagement strategy;
- Role in implementation.

The purpose of this structure is to map the key stakeholders, understand their interests and level of influence, and define the appropriate engagement and management strategies for collaboration. This approach supports co-creation and participatory project implementation, while taking into account individual motivations, particularly for stakeholder groups whose contributions are voluntary.

For the WPs, completing this analysis was optional, since the extent to which each WP involves stakeholders beyond project partners varies significantly.

Step 2: Stakeholder list

The stakeholder list builds upon the stakeholder analysis and provides a detailed register of specific stakeholders involved in the project. For each stakeholder, the following information is collected:

- Stakeholder name / organisation;
- Type (e.g. policy, research, farmer, advisor, etc.);
- Country / region;
- Contact person or responsible partner;
- Involvement level / role;
- Status / engagement update.

This list supports the monitoring and coordination of collaboration among project participants, partners, and related organisations. It can be regularly updated to reflect new activities and changes in stakeholder engagement over time.

Step 3: Logframe Matrix

The Logframe Matrix is the core element of the LFA. It represents the project's logical framework, organising its hierarchy of objectives, indicators, sources of verification, and assumptions in a structured and transparent way.

The Logframe Matrix is structured into three main levels:

1. Overall Goal / Impact – the long-term effect to which the project contributes;
2. Outcome/Purpose – the direct objective(s) expected to be achieved by the end of the project.
3. Outputs /Results – the tangible deliverables and results produced by project activities.

The three main levels are complemented by additional elements:

- Indicators: measurable variables used to assess progress and performance;
- Risks / Assumptions: external factors that may influence the achievement of results.

LOGFRAME MATRIX <i>(scroll down for example)</i>			
SUMMARY		INDICATORS	RISKS / ASSUMPTIONS
GOAL (impact)	<i>Strategic intent: What are we trying to accomplish? What is the overall broader impact to which the action will contribute?</i>	<i>What are the key indicators related to the overall goal?</i>	<i>What are the external factors necessary to sustain objectives in the long term?</i>
OUTCOME (purpose)	<i>What is the immediate outcome at the end of the project?</i>	<i>Which indicators show that the objective of the action has been achieved?</i>	<i>Which external factors and conditions are necessary to achieve that objective?</i>
OUTPUTS (exp. results)	<i>What are the deliverable results envisaged to achieve the specific objectives?</i>	<i>What are the indicators to measure whether and to what extent the action achieves the expected results?</i>	<i>What preconditions are required before the action starts?</i>

Figure 3. General Logframe Matrix template for the WPs (own creation based on EC template (2025))

This integrated structure ensures a coherent link between planning and monitoring, allowing for a clear documentation of the project’s logical framework and providing a solid basis for performance and impact assessment.

Step 4: Activities

The detailed activities related to the previous steps are presented in a separate section, which focuses on specific actions and includes the annual activity plan and monitoring table for each WP.

For each detailed activity, the following information is documented:

- Activity: name or description of the specific action;
- Responsible partner: the partner in charge of implementation;
- Connection to tasks: link to related project tasks;

- Deadline: planned completion date;
- Indicators: measurable metrics to assess progress;
- Means of verification: type of evidence used for verification (e.g. workshop, document, report);
- Risks / Assumptions: external factors influencing implementation;
- Status: current progress status (e.g. ongoing, completed);
- Progress / Achievements: short summary of results achieved;
- Difficulties during implementation: challenges encountered during execution.

This sheet presents the operational-level implementation of tasks related to each WP and is directly linked to the logical structure of the Logframe Matrix. The structure allows WP leaders to update progress regularly, typically on an annual basis, ensuring consistent and transparent monitoring across the project.

Overall, the LFA serves as an integrated tracking instrument that links strategic objectives with annual activities, ensures the monitoring of stakeholder engagement and analysis. The yearly updates support a continuous and comparable evaluation throughout the entire duration of the project.

2.3 Logframe Matrix development process

The first step in this process was the preparation of the Logframe Matrix Guideline (available on SharePoint upon request), which outlined the principles and structure for developing the Logframe Matrix. This guideline was presented and discussed during the Kick-off Meeting held in Budapest on 5 March 2024.

The development of the Logframe Matrices took place through several coordinated steps, under the overall coordination of ÖMKi:

1. Templates and harmonization: ÖMKi provided common templates to ensure that all Logframe Matrices followed a consistent structure.
2. Logframe Matrix development: WP leaders (as well as TWG and HUB Coordinators), developed their respective matrices in collaboration with their partners and members. For WPs, this process was simpler, as a lot of information could be used from and build on the GA.
3. Integration and review: The deadline for the development was 31 May 2024, all WPs, TWGs, and HUBs completed their Logframe Matrix complementing it with the yearly activities. The first review took place between December 2024 - January 2025, capturing the results of Year 1 and the plans for Year 2.
4. Reflection: During the Annual Meeting in April 2025, a joint reflection session was organised to present a status overview of the project, including the progress of the WPs, HUBs and TWGs based on the Logframe Matrices, highlighting commonalities and areas for improvement, which together form the basis of this deliverable.

As a result of this process, each WP, TWG, and HUB now has a *living Logframe Matrix*, which is a dynamic planning and monitoring tool that can be updated annually.

Thus, the development of the Logframe Matrices was not merely an administrative task but became a core element of the project's learning and capacity-building process, strengthening coherence, reflection, and adaptive management across all levels of BOOST4BIOEAST.

2.4 Analytical framework

This report reviews the Logframe Matrices of the eight WPs of the BOOST4BIOEAST project:

- WP1 - Coordination and management;
- WP2 - Development of national BIOEAST HUBs;
- WP3 - Enriching macro-regional and national knowledge on bioeconomy-related competencies and biomass;
- WP4 - Mobilising innovation and finance sources for BIOEAST;
- WP5 - Boosting Bioeconomy Education, Learning & BIOEAST Unit Net;
- WP6 - Boosting the work in TWGs and seeking alignment with HUBs;
- WP7 - Development of bioeconomy Action Plans in the HUBs;
- WP8 - Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication.

The comparative analysis of the Logframe Matrices follows a step-by-step approach, assessing each matrix with respect to **six key structural elements** of the LFA against the GA requirements:

- **Stakeholders and communication channels:** the actors (task leaders, project partners, potential stakeholders not involved in the project) with whom the WPs work closely;
- **Goals:** It describes what the WPs ultimately aim to accomplish and the broader impact that the outcomes will contribute to over the long term. It is not about short-term outputs, but about the wider transformation the project seeks to support;
- **Outcomes:** the direct objective(s) expected by the end of the project. It expresses the concrete overall result that should be observable once all planned activities are completed and all outputs are achieved;
- **Outputs:** tangible deliverables produced through the project's activities. They represent the products, services, tools, reports, events, or other measurable results that are necessary to achieve the project's outcome.
- **Indicators:** key measurable metrics that demonstrate progress toward the overall goal, confirm whether the specific objective has been achieved, and assess whether and to what extent the action delivers the expected results.

- **Risks/assumptions:** key external factors and conditions required to achieve the objective and sustain it in the long term, including the critical preconditions that must be in place before the action starts.

The first-year activities are not addressed in this deliverable. Their evaluation will be included in the final report (*D1.5 -LogFrame Methodology Second Progress Report* due in M36), which will summarise all three project years.

The analysis enabled the identification of gaps, misalignments, extra elements connected to WP activities but not detailed in the GA and out-of-scope elements, all informing further harmonisation and improvement.

This uniform approach ensures:

- **Comparability across WPs:** With eight WPs focusing on distinct areas, a standardised framework was essential to maintain analytical consistency and enable matrix-by-matrix comparison.
- **Alignment with the GA:** The selected categories mirror the conceptual structure outlined in the GA, ensuring coherence with the project's theoretical and strategic foundations.
- **Clarity for stakeholders:** Organising the review around key functional dimensions helps WP Leads and partners to easily grasp the overall logic of each WP, recognise its strengths and gaps in implementation, and support effective monitoring and future updates.

The following chapters provide detailed analyses under these categories, complemented by a comparative summary table highlighting the key features across all Logframe Matrices.

3 Stakeholder involvement analysis

3.1 Type of stakeholders

The stakeholder engagement pattern in BOOST4BIOEAST reflects the project's multi-stakeholder and co-creation logic, where different groups contribute to strategy, implementation, and knowledge transfer. The BOOST4BIOEAST project brings together a wide range of institutional actors from the BIOEAST macro-region. These stakeholder groups contribute their expertise and capacities across various thematic areas and activities organized under the project's WPs.

This chapter outlines the types of institutions engaged in each WP and Table 1 indicates which stakeholder types are involved directly in which WPs, allowing to identify commonalities, differences, and gaps in participation.

Table 1. Types of stakeholders involved in each WP, marked with "x"

Type of stakeholders	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8
All partners of the consortium	x							x
External Ethics Advisors	x							
Project Officer (PO)	x							
BIOEAST Secretary and Board	x	x				x		x
HUB Coordinators	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
TWG Coordinators	x	x		x		x	x	x
Research organisations*			x	x	x	x		x
Policy makers*		x	x	x	x	x		x
Funding bodies/funding organisations*				x		x		x
Bioeconomy companies*			x	x	x	x		x
Bioeconomy start-ups*				x		x		x
Investors*				x		x		x
Universities*			x		x	x		x
Chambers of commerce*			x		x	x		x
Civil society organisations*						x		x
Farmers' associations*			x					

* External actors, not part of the consortium

WP1 (Coordination and management) involves mainly strategic and management related actors, including the BIOEAST Secretary and Board, External Ethics Advisors, HUB and TWG Coordinators, as well as the project partners (research organisations, ministries, universities, civil society organisations). Their engagement corresponds to WP1's purpose of ensuring effective coordination of the project, alignment with the GA, and oversight of the entire project. The dominance of coordination-level stakeholders is appropriate, and the limited inclusion of external or practical stakeholders reflects WP1's purely administrative and governance nature. However, WP1 is also responsible for maintaining and building collaboration with other similar projects in cooperation with WP8 and attending related events which means that indirectly the WP is connected to a wide range of stakeholders.

WP2 (Development of national BIOEAST HUBs) shows the broadest stakeholder diversity, consistent with its co-creation and capacity-building focus. HUB Coordinators are the central actors, involving wide range of stakeholders such as research organisations, public authorities, industries, civil society organisations etc. Their inclusion matches the WP's goal to operationalise multi-stakeholder HUBs and stimulates national bioeconomy ecosystems. The relatively wide representation across academic, policy, and practice levels indicates strong alignment with the participatory design of HUBs. In addition to HUB Coordinators, the capacity building activities in WP2 also involve TWG Coordinators.

WP3's (Enriching macro-regional and national knowledge on bioeconomy-related competencies and biomass) stakeholder landscape is narrower, focusing mainly on HUB Coordinators. This pattern fits the WP's analytical and evidence-based mission, such as the data collection, mapping, and assessment of bioeconomy resources and competencies. The strong involvement of research-oriented actors ensures methodological robustness, and the engagement of industry or regional authorities and policy makers will support the direct application of data in policy or business contexts. As the WP3 works in close collaboration with the HUB Coordinators, maintaining continuous contact with all HUB actors, who themselves represent a broad and diverse range of stakeholders.

WP4 (Mobilising innovation and finance sources for BIOEAST) engages HUB and TWG Coordinators, research organisations, and private-sector actors. The inclusion of these groups supports the WP's aim to stimulate innovation, mobilise funding, and connect start-ups and established firms through the Open Innovation Challenge (OIC) and the Pitching Events. The participation of financial institutions and business support organisations highlights a potential for investment mobilisation. The focus on youth and start-ups suggests an opportunity for more targeted engagement of educational and entrepreneurial networks.

Stakeholder involvement in **WP5** (Boosting Bioeconomy Education, Learning & BIOEAST Unit Net) is centred on research organisations, universities, and HUB Coordinators, consistent with its educational focus. The strong academic participation ensures the scientific quality of outputs

such as the collection of bioeconomy education materials, curricula mapping and the development of the Knowledge Platform. However, through the operation and the sharing of materials via the Platform, it is indirectly connected to numerous stakeholder groups.

The main stakeholders of **WP6** (Boosting the work in TWGs and seeking alignment with HUBs) are the TWG Coordinators, but in line with the WP's objectives, there is also close collaboration with the HUB Coordinators. The stronger involvement of researchers and policymakers stems from the fact that the TWGs are structurally centred around these two stakeholder types. Moreover, WP6's core objectives - the update of the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) and the organisation of science-policy dialogues - naturally position these groups as the primary target audiences. Cooperation with the HUBs is also an essential component of WP6, and they are therefore involved in several sub-processes. Finally, one of the main outcomes of this WP, the SRIA, is a key reference document for funder organisations at both national and EU levels, making their inclusion in the related processes equally crucial. However, beyond this, the process of developing and validating the SRIA will be fully open to all stakeholders and will seek to actively involve them throughout the progress.

WP7 (Development of bioeconomy Action Plans in the HUBs) is heavily anchored in HUB Coordination but TWG Coordinators are involved at later phases. This composition fits its task of developing national bioeconomy Action Plans (APs) and aligning them with SRIA processes. Through the HUBs and TWGs, indirectly a wide range of stakeholders are included in the work but the main actors in this WP are the HUB and TWG Coordinators themselves. The main outcome of this WP, the national APs, primarily targets policymakers, however diverse stakeholder groups are involved in its development. In addition, involving policymakers in the workshops dedicated to co-developing the AP is of utmost importance to ensure relevance, ownership, and policy uptake.

WP8 (Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication) demonstrates extensive inclusion of all stakeholders. This broad representation aligns with WP8's role in ensuring visibility, knowledge dissemination, and outreach of the overall project. The wide communication and dissemination help to ensure that output reaches different stakeholder communities, from policymakers to practitioners across various regions in Europe.

Cross-WP Observations

HUB and TWG Coordinators are omnipresent across all WPs, confirming their integrative role as the backbone of project governance and implementation. Research organisations participate in WPs 2, 4, 5, 6, and 8, showing strong involvement in methodological, educational, and dissemination activities. External stakeholders such as private sector, financial institutions, and civil society appear to be more involved indirectly but have a strong role in WP2, WP4, WP6, WP7 and WP8. Policy-level actors are consistently represented in WPs 2, 6, and 7, reflecting the project's governance- and science-policy oriented aims and activities.

3.2 Comparison of the different communication channels across the WPs

During the first half of the BOOST4BIOEAST project (until July 2025), communication with stakeholders was organised through structured and regular channels aligned with the specific objectives of each WP.

Within **WP1**, internal communication among consortium members was ensured through bi-monthly online consortium and Executive Committee (ExCom) meetings, annual in-person meetings, monthly project management team sessions within the Coordination Team (ÖMKI & SIE) and bi-weekly communication activity meetings with Communications Team (APRE, TRUST-IT, ÖMKI and SIE). Continuous coordination was maintained via a shared SharePoint workspace, and regular e-mail exchanges. The BIOEAST Board and Secretary were contacted through formal channels upon request, while the PO and the External Ethics Advisor were involved through regular e-mail communication and participation in online or annual meetings.

In **WP2**, HUB Coordinators met bi-monthly at the HUB Coordination Body Meetings, while TWG Coordinators maintained regular communication via e-mail. Policy makers, including but not limited to BIOEAST Board members, were reached through formal e-mail exchanges and at least one interministerial meeting organised annually within each HUB.

WP3 engaged with national and regional policy makers, government agencies, farmers' and bio-based industry associations, chambers of commerce, universities, and research organisations primarily through the HUBs, which served as the key interface for dialogue and cooperation. The HUB Coordinators were engaged through regular online consultations or e-mail exchanges.

Under **WP4**, project partners, Task Leaders, and the WP Leader maintained contact through e-mails, occasional online meetings, and personal interactions at conferences. Research institutions, policy stakeholders and funding bodies were involved via informational inquiries and interviews, while engagement with bioeconomy start-ups and investors was facilitated through the BioeconomyVentures network.

Communication within **WP5** with national and regional policy makers, bio-based industry associations, chambers of commerce, universities and research organisation took place via HUBs and the TWG Bioeconomy Education.

In **WP6**, TWG Coordinators were supported by regular bi-monthly online meetings and annual in-person gatherings held during the BIOEAST Bioeconomy Conferences together with the HUBs. TWG members participated in at least two online meetings per year organized by each TWG. The WP6 related events (science-policy dialogues, SRIA update) were disseminated through social media channels, website and direct e-mails.

Finally, **WP8** ensured broader external communication and dissemination towards wide range of stakeholders as designed and laid down in D8.1 (*Communication and Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy*) and D8.2 (*Communication and Dissemination and Exploitation Activities*)

Report). These stakeholders are primarily reached through a mix of channels such as website, HUB-minipage articles, social media posts, newsletters, webinars, in-person events, synergy workshops, and dedicated communication materials, ensuring wide visibility and engagement across the BIOEAST community.

Cross-WP observations

The stakeholder involvement pattern across BOOST4BIOEAST WPs largely reflects a well-balanced mix between coordination, research, and policy actors. However, participation from industry, business, finance, and civil society-oriented stakeholders could be expanded to reinforce innovation, investment, and societal impact. Strengthening these links would further enhance the project's capacity to bridge strategic vision with practical implementation and to sustain the BIOEAST macro-regional bioeconomy beyond the project's lifetime.

3.3 Identified gaps compared to the GA

Overall, the identification of stakeholders broadly reflects what is set out in the GA, but some gaps can be observed. In **WP2**, although the primary interaction is with HUB and TWG Coordinators, the WP also reaches a much wider group of external stakeholders within (e.g. national HUB meetings) and beyond the HUBs (e.g. through the Annual Bioeconomy Conference) yet these groups are not included in the stakeholder analysis. In **WP5**, the TWG Coordinators were overlooked, despite their clear involvement in activities such as the mapping of educational materials and the expansion or promotion of the Knowledge Platform. The list of communication channels also misses several key actors, including the other TWGs and the Knowledge Platform itself, which functions as a key channel for knowledge transfer and information sharing among a wide range of stakeholders, in addition, communication with the Network of bioeconomy universities in Central and Eastern Europe (UniNet) is likewise not highlighted. In **WP7**, only a stakeholder list is provided, without specifying the different communication channels. However, at the beginning of the WP, HUB Coordinators were actively involved in developing the AP methodology - through email exchanges, bilateral meetings, and a joint online workshop dedicated to finalising the methodology. Currently, regular bi-weekly AP consultations and e-mail communication are maintained with HUB Coordinators, yet these channels are not reflected in the current stakeholder mapping.

4 Assessment of the Goals, Outcomes, Outputs, Indicators and Risks

The following chapter presents the Logframe Matrix prepared by the WP and Task Leads and compares it with the main objectives defined in the project's GA, focusing on the Goal, Outcome, and Output levels, as well as the identified Risks and Indicators. Long-term goals, outcomes and outputs, indicators and risks of WPs are summarised in Table 2.

Table 2. Long-term and strategic goals, outcomes and outputs of WPs

WPs	GOAL	OUTCOME	OUTPUT	INDICATORS	RISKS
WP1 Coordination and management	The project is implemented according to the GA to best support the BIOEAST Initiative in reaching its mission and objectives laid down in the Vision Paper.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The project will successfully reach its end by 2026. All consortium partners will work in accordance with the GA, Consortium Agreement (CA), and the project work plan. Financial costs will remain aligned with the GA. The consortium will avoid bankruptcies and misalignments. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Steer the project at strategic levels to ensure that it reaches its objectives, delivers outputs and maintains close collaboration with the BIOEAST Board and Secretary. Logframes for WP monitoring are completed. CA signed by all partners. The project's 29 deliverables & 17 milestones, and financial statements are submitted on time with high quality onto EC portal. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Partners submit the necessary information to ÖMKi and SIE for monitoring WP progress and financial status. Progress of WPs follows the Year 1 plans as outlined in the Logframe monitoring matrices. Partners follow the financial guidelines and instructions provided by SIE. Partners comply with all processes and procedures defined in the GA and CA. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Partners may not provide the necessary information on time, affecting monitoring and reporting. Errors or deviations may occur in the official financial statements during Reporting Periods. Quality of information submitted by partners may be insufficient. Delays or gaps in preparing and using the required monitoring and reporting templates (Logframe templates by ÖMKi; biannual template and reporting guidelines by SIE).
WP2 Development of national BIOEAST HUBs	Set up long-lasting structures for cooperation and networking at national and macro-regional levels. Connect bioeconomy stakeholders with policy makers and strengthen their engagement in bioeconomy policy, research, and innovation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There will be 11 functioning HUBs in the BIOEAST countries. HUBs will involve active participation from bioeconomy stakeholder groups. HUBs will actively contribute to the development of national bioeconomy APs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A HUB Coordination Body and the 9 National HUBs are created. 2-3+ National Mirror groups per country are active. Interministerial connections are established. HUB stakeholders are trained in bioeconomy skills and competencies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> APs developed. Diverse stakeholder representation within the HUBs. Organisation of national science-to-policy events. Policy-maker recommendations on the HUBs' policy support activities. Regular HUB meetings and activities carried out. Meetings of the HUB Coordination Body. Kick-off meetings conducted. At least one interministerial meeting organised per year. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Internal and external stakeholders may not be sufficiently engaged. HUBs may not achieve adequate visibility at national, macro-regional, or international levels. Delays in the timely kick-off of HUBs or lack of a clear methodological approach. Insufficient coordination within the HUB Coordination Body. Limited engagement of HUB Coordinators and stakeholders in HUB activities.
WP3 Enriching macro-regional and national	Inform (policy) stakeholders through enriched macro-regional and national knowledge on	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Comprehensive, harmonized tools and indicators will be developed for mapping and continuously monitoring bioeconomy competencies and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Comprehensive desk research will identify best practices, challenges, and sample indicators for bioeconomy competencies and biomass mapping. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Methodology is shared with governmental bodies and agencies across the BIOEAST macro-region via HUB Coordinators. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited visibility and uptake of the developed methodologies. Key policymakers may not be sufficiently reached during the indicator definition process.

bioeconomy-related competencies and available biomass through the development of better methodologies to promote information-based policy making and enable long-term planning for bio-based industry actors.

available biomass at the (regional and) national levels across the BIOEAST macro-region and the rest of Europe.

- All HUBs represented in the project will use the provided methodology and indicators, resulting in structured and comparable data and information.

- A set of defined and prioritised bioeconomy and biomass indicators will be developed by HUB Coordinators through workshops, consortium consultations and literature review.
- A clear methodology for indicator utilisation, including required data, examples, and definitions will be developed.
- Data and application of indicators will be collected through HUBs.
- Pilot testing of methodologies will be carried out in Romania and Slovakia.
- Expert assessment on the developed indicators will be conducted via HUB consultations.
- A gap analysis will be conducted to compare status quo and desired values with the application of an Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) structure.
- Stakeholder feedback will be collected and analysed through HUBs (questionnaires).
- Desirable policy recommendation formats will be identified.
- Policy recommendations will be validated.

Results accessible on the Knowledge Platform.

- Report on bioeconomy-related competences, biomass availability and uses.
- Integrated assessment describing competences and biomass indices.
- Policy recommendations on biomass and competences.
- Guideline containing the final list of indicators, their descriptions, and the assessment methodology.
- Two pilot mapping processes implemented with test HUBs (Romania and Slovakia).
- One AHP analysis per country, including gap analysis and index development.
- Two online surveys conducted.
- Eleven national online workshops on policy recommendations organised by HUBs.
- One macro-regional written consultation and validation process completed.

- Delays or gaps in completing preparatory tasks or collecting preliminary data from stakeholders through the HUBs.
- Insufficient participation or feedback from HUB coordinators and experts.

**WP4
Mobilising
innovation and
finance sources
for BIOEAST**

Greater awareness among decision-makers, bioeconomy innovation actors and networks, improved knowledge among research, development and innovation (RDI) organisations and businesses about funding opportunities,

- An overview of the bioeconomy innovation landscape will be provided, along with recommendations for policymakers on how to shape support policies and financial instruments to maximise bioeconomy innovation potential.
- Bioeconomy solutions to important technological, managerial, or social challenges

- The state of the art of the bioeconomy-related innovation ecosystem in BIOEAST countries will be introduced, covering national and regional strategies, stakeholders and their networks, initiatives, projects, and funding/financing opportunities.
- The BIOEAST OIC will be organised.
- Startup-to-investor pitching events with national and international private and public investors will be organised.

- Investments in bioeconomy innovation and business activities.
- Existence of more targeted and effective strategies and policy programmes supporting bioeconomy innovation.
- Number of new enterprises and the intensity of competition in bioeconomy.
- Innovation performance of bioeconomy sectors.

- Limited outreach to bioeconomy stakeholders beyond standard dissemination activities.
- Insufficient follow-up research and knowledge-sharing activities.
- Poor coordination or timing of dissemination efforts.
- Low receptiveness of targeted stakeholders.
- Limited participation from external stakeholders, including start-ups and investors.

	<p>enhanced cooperation and capital mobilisation for bioeconomy innovation, and a stronger commitment of younger generations to the bioeconomy transition.</p>	<p>relevant to the macro-region will be identified.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Talented HUB networks will be attracted to strengthen regional bioeconomy innovation. • Awareness of the potential of bioeconomy sectors among young generations, including universities and UniNet, will be increased. • Networking opportunities will be fostered to accelerate knowledge flows, helping to bridge funding opportunities and the bioeconomy innovation gap. • The macro-region's bioeconomy growth potential at both proof-of-concept (start-up) and growth (scale-up) stages will be improved, leveraging Bioeconomy Ventures and MPowerBIO projects. 		<p>One dissemination event presenting the innovation ecosystem mapping results.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informational email sent to stakeholders announcing the publication of the mapping deliverable. • News post published about the mapping results on BIOEAST's website (also shared on social media). • Dissemination and networking activities carried out. • Five pitching events organised. • At least 10 start-ups participating in pitching events. • At least 2 investors participating in pitching events. • One multi-stakeholder workshop on funding and financing needs and opportunities in bioeconomy thematic areas. • One innovation ecosystem mapping report produced. • OIC Task Force established (including one internal challenge design session and one consensus workshop for validation). • Number of OIC participants. • Number of OIC winners. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insufficient staff capacities. • Lack of reliable and up-to-date data sources. • Tightly scheduled research activities creating delays or bottlenecks. • Limited interest from potential OIC participants. • Dependence on HUBs' knowledge-transfer and networking activities. • Dependence on WP3's assessment of national competences.
<p>WP5 Boosting Bioeconomy Education, Learning &</p>	<p>More research and innovation priorities identified in the BIOEAST region will be integrated into national agendas and influence regional and EU investments, while</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A completed mapping reflecting the priorities will be delivered. • An operational UniNet will be established. • An operational Knowledge Platform will be developed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP5 activities will be communicated through channels outside the project to generate discussions and bottom-up dialogue. • Regional specificities, particularities, interests, and priorities will be detected and identified in cooperation with the regional HUBs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Completion of the UniNet Action Plan. • One funded EU project achieved for the UniNet. • Number of references on the Knowledge Platform. • Number of users of the Knowledge Platform. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insufficient visibility of the produced materials. • Inadequate dissemination and communication strategy for reaching target groups. • Delays in completing intermediate and preparatory steps within required timeframes.

	<p>UniNet's cooperation in developing joint curricula and engaging in EU-funded projects, together with a functional Knowledge Platform operating beyond the project's lifetime, will ensure long-term impact and sustainability.</p>			<p>Deliverable 4.1 WP deliverables.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication of WP outcomes through various channels. • Indicators defined in the BOOST4BIOEAST deliverables and monitoring framework. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulty in mobilising a sufficient number of relevant experts. • Failure to identify or leverage parallel events and related actions. • Challenges in integrating discussions into a broader, coherent context. • Underuse or weak engagement with the Knowledge Platform and its dynamics.
<p>WP6 Boosting the work in TWGs and seeking alignment with HUBs</p>	<p>Many of the BIOEAST research directions and needs identified in the macro-region will feed into national agendas, initiatives, funding sources and investments in the CEE region and the EU more broadly and will also have an impact on macro-regional scientific innovation policy.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The continuity of the functioning TWGs will be ensured, including their scope on preparing updated thematic SRIAs. • Seven issue papers (one per TWG) on specific bioeconomy topics will be developed. • HUB and TWG sustainability strategies will be co-constructed. • A policy brief will be prepared with recommendations on how to engage and enable policymakers to actively participate in developing and synchronizing bioeconomy strategies along the different themes (SRIAs included). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussions will be generated to develop a bottom-up, stakeholder-driven approach for identifying synergies and complementarities between the bioeconomy sectors of BIOEAST countries and identifying region-specific research topics and strategic directions. • TWGs will align their work with the HUBs to ensure strategic cooperation and to strengthen information exchange and communication between policymakers and experts on priority research topics at the macro-regional level. • TWGs and HUBs will develop roadmaps (internal activity plans) for monitoring and evaluating their activities, aligned with their specific goals, outputs, and expected outcomes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thematic research topics incorporated into national or EU research calls. • Three validation workshops organised. • Prepared documents: -Updated SRIA, -7 issue papers, -1 policy brief, • Organisation of consultation activities: -2 macro-regional workshops per TWG, -11 national consultations, -Three science-policy dialogues per TWG, -Individual interviews with national policymakers. • 18 Logframe matrices prepared for TWGs and HUBs + sustainability strategies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insufficient visibility and dissemination of the prepared materials to relevant institutions. • Delays in completing preparatory tasks, leaving inadequate time for data integration. • Difficulty in mobilising a sufficiently large and relevant group of external experts.

<p>WP7</p> <p>Development of bioeconomy Action Plans in the HUBs</p>	<p>To make progress and have an impact on the national bioeconomy strategy developments in the BIOEAST countries both at stakeholder and policymaking level.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The level of involvement of stakeholders and policymakers (especially the BIOEAST Board) in bioeconomy strategizing efforts will be enhanced. The futures literacy competence of project participants will be improved. The adaptivity of bioeconomy APs and policy goals across a range of plausible EU-level development scenarios will be increased. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The pilot tested AP methodology will be adopted by the HUBs. Eleven future-proofed APs of the BIOEAST countries, aligned with the SRIA, will be developed. 	<p>Start of the implementation of the APs.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> APs recognised by the relevant BIOEAST HUBs and policymakers (BIOEAST Board and WP2 interministerial groups). Methodology tested and improved based on feedback and application. APs finalised and approved by the HUBs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Insufficient ownership or inadequate funding. Limited engagement or weak commitment from HUB members and policymakers. Inadequate cooperation between the HUBs and the WP7 team.
<p>WP8</p> <p>Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication</p>	<p>Maximise the project's impact and visibility and stimulate the decision-making processes towards the bioeconomy transition in the BIOEAST macro-region.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) strategy that encompasses all project needs for promotion and further use of results will be developed. A series of activities and tools that increase awareness of bioeconomy processes and practices at the local level in the interested regions will be implemented. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The application of the DEC Strategy will explain in detail to partners how to proceed in their activities. A consistent project identity will be maintained to highlight and strengthen the implementation and visibility of project results. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased overall visibility of the project and improved dissemination of objectives. Achievement of project Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for all communication materials and tools. Publication of nine policy briefs and papers. Organisation or participation in more than three webinars or events. Growth in project following and wider dissemination or referencing of project results. Effective outreach to all identified target groups. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited adaptability of the DEC plan or challenges in implementing its activities and materials effectively. Incoherent project branding or visual identity, or incorrect planning/distribution of communication and dissemination materials. Policy briefs are not adequately reflecting findings from webinars and project activities. Low participation in events or insufficient visibility. Ineffective or inconsistent implementation of strategic communication actions. Difficulty adapting to changes in communication needs or context. Use of an inappropriate tone of voice for key target audiences. Missed opportunities to participate in relevant events.

4.1 Gaps and misalignments

In this section, the gaps and misalignments identified in the WPs' Logframe Matrix are examined in comparison with the information provided in GA. In addition, elements going beyond GA activities are also identified. These are detailed in Table 3.

Table 3. Gaps and misalignments between goals, outcomes and outputs of WPs' Logframe Matrices and GA

WP	Category	Reference from the GA	Gaps compared to GA	Misalignments with the GA	Extra Elements
WP1	Goals	-	-	-	-
	Outcomes	-	-	-	-
	Outputs	-	-	-	-
	Risks	Stakeholders' reluctance to engage with the project.	This risk is not mentioned.	The usage of internal and official financial reporting periods is confusing. The submission of official financial statements is mentioned in the risks when these are not required being as a lump-sum CSA.	-
	Indicators	-	-	-	-
WP2	Goals	-	-	-	-
	Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To support TWGs with identified stakeholders' needs and national opportunities. To animate cross-HUB collaboration at the macro-region level. 	These risks are not mentioned.	-	-
	Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organisation of capacity building programme for HUB and TWG Coordinators. Organisation of Annual Bioeconomy Conferences. 	Lack of reference to Annual Bioeconomy Conferences and the course catalogue for capacity-building as key expected outputs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The capacity building mentioned as a training for bioeconomy skills and competencies. However, this should focus on necessary skills and competencies to run and animate national HUBs and TWGs. Missing specification that National Mirror Groups must be 	-

			aligned with the thematic areas of the TWGs.	
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mislabeling of "national science-policy events": these should be clarified as national meetings for science-policy development within the interministerial process. 	
	Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fail to connect with allied or similar bioeconomy projects/ organisations/ networks in the HUBs. Delays in national HUB establishment affecting different WP result delivery negatively. Obstacles created by public administrations and authorities in the forms of bureaucratic barriers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No mention of the risk that HUBs may struggle to connect with similar initiatives, limiting synergies and knowledge exchange. Absence of the risk related to administrative or institutional obstacles (e.g., bureaucratic barriers) that could hinder implementation. No acknowledgment of the potential impact of delays in setting up the HUBs, which could affect the work and timelines of several other WPs. 	-
	Indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 30-50 bioeconomy stakeholders involved/BIOEAST HUB. 	As a key KPI in the project, number of stakeholders is missing.	-
WP3	Goals	-	-	-
	Outcomes	To create and apply a common framework to identify and assess biomass feedstocks and their uses, and bioeconomy-related competencies, required for a sustainable transition in the BIOEAST at national level.	-	GA focuses on methodology delivery, while Logframe Matrix emphasizes integrated indices and comprehensive reporting.
	Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Multidimensional assessment of bioeconomy competences, biomass availability. Policy recommendations. 	-	The outputs listed as a task list rather than the main expected results of WP3.
	Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unavailable data at national level. Delays with the organization / low attendance at national workshops. 	These risks are not identified.	-
	Indicators	-	-	-
WP4	Goals	-	-	-

	Outcomes	-	-	-	-
	Outputs	-	-	-	-
	Risks	Insufficient quality of the pitching events from the hosts.	This risk is not mentioned.	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Staff capacity limitation. • Proper coordination, communication and time management. • HUBs' knowledge transfer and networking activities. • WP3 assessment of national competences. • Reliable and up-to-date data sources. • Tightly scheduled research activities.
	Indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bioeconomy innovation ecosystem package (with 11 subsections, 1 per country) (policy briefs, funding, and financing opportunities recommendations). • 1 evaluation report per country of the OIC. • 20 start-ups supported. 	As key WP deliverables, bioeconomy innovation ecosystem package and evaluation report of the OIC are missing.	Only 10 startups and 2 investors are mentioned.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovation performance of bioeconomy sectors. • One dissemination event presenting the innovation ecosystem mapping results. • Informational email sent to stakeholders announcing the publication of the mapping deliverable. • News post published about the mapping results on BIOEAST's website (also shared on social media). • Dissemination and networking activities carried out. • Number of pitching events (5). • 1 multi-stakeholder workshop. • 1 innovation ecosystem mapping report. • OIC Task Force. • Number of OIC participants. • Number of OIC winners.
WP5	Goals	Facilitating the development of inclusive national bioeconomy APs through such as dedicated bioeconomy programmes in education.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identifying educational needs related to bioeconomy and map existing knowledge and educational materials as a key goal is missing. • Enhancing the BIOEAST UniNet, supporting interaction 	Identifying research and innovation priorities (WP6) in BIOEAST and influencing EU investments (WP4) are not part of WP5's goals.	Organising the UniNet curricula and participating in EU-funded projects are mentioned as new goals.

		<p>and cooperation with European Bioeconomy University (EBU) and European Community of Practice on Bioeconomy Education (Ica-CoP) is missing.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Developing the roadmap for BIOEAST UniNet and aligning with the ongoing educational priorities in the wider domain of bioeconomy is missing. 		
Outcomes	To develop a roadmap for BIOEAST UniNet by providing alignment with the ongoing educational priorities in the wider domain of bioeconomy.	UniNet is only generally mentioned, though that's an integral part of the WP.	-	-
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mapping of educational needs and materials. Expansion of the UniNet. Policy makers engaged across bioeconomy sectors through interministerial groups to achieve policy coherence. Development of BIOEAST Knowledge Platform. 	Interministerial meetings are not mentioned.	The outputs listed by WP5 do not correspond to the GA or the scope of WP5.	-
Risks	Lack of interest in BIOEAST Knowledge Platform.	-	Proper dissemination and communication strategy and delays in content creation are mentioned, however this belongs to WP8.	-
Indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3 additional universities joined the BIOEAST UniNet. 1 Roadmap for BIOEAST UniNet. 1 BIOEAST Knowledge Platform & 11 online national mini-sites HUBs. 10000 visitors in the BIOEAST Knowledge Platform during the project. 	The indicators are not listed at all, only the development of deliverables in general.	-	-
Goals	-	-	-	-
WP6 Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To ensure the continuity of the functioning TWG. To align the work of TWGs with the HUBs for AP development and SRIA update. To ensure strategic cooperation among the TWGs and HUBs to improve and strengthen the exchange and communication between policymakers and experts. 	-	The outputs and outcomes have been reversed.	-

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To develop roadmaps and sustainability plans for HUBs and TWGs. 											
	Outputs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Updated thematic SRIAs and BIOEAST SRIA. TWG evaluation and incorporation of national mirror groups. Development of policy briefs and issue papers. 	-	The outputs and outcomes have been reversed.	-								
	Risks <p>Difficulties in refreshing TWGs and putting in place the SRIA update process.</p>	This risk is not mentioned.	-	-								
	Indicators <p>Stakeholder involvement (20/TWG)</p>	The number of stakeholders involved through TWGs is not specified.	-	-								
WP7	Goals <p>Facilitating the development of inclusive national bioeconomy APs.</p>	-	It uses the term “strategy development,” but WP7 is actually concerned with AP development.	-								
	Outcomes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To find and address interlinkages between the SRIAs and bioeconomy APs. To provide a universal, yet versatile, methodological framework. 	The interlinkages with SRIA and methodology framework development are missing.	The outputs and outcomes have been slightly reversed.	-								
	Outputs <p>Developed national APs.</p>	-	The outputs and outcomes have been slightly reversed.	-								
	Risks <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Insufficient engagement of stakeholders in APs development. Delayed/underperforming outcomes from WP7. 	-	-	Insufficient ownership and funding are added as new risks.								
	Indicators <p>-</p>	-	-	-								
WP8	Goals <p>-</p>	-	-	-								
	Outcomes <p>-</p>	-	-	-	Outputs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Maintain collaboration with bioeconomy projects. Organisation of science-policy dialogues. Launch of the mini-HUB sites. 	Collaboration with bioeconomy projects, the organization of science-policy dialogues and mini-HUB sites are missing.	-	-	Risks <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Insufficient participation of policymakers. HUBs are not collaborating in producing suitable information to be promoted. 	Policymakers and HUBs involvement are not mentioned.	-	-
	Outputs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Maintain collaboration with bioeconomy projects. Organisation of science-policy dialogues. Launch of the mini-HUB sites. 	Collaboration with bioeconomy projects, the organization of science-policy dialogues and mini-HUB sites are missing.	-	-								
Risks <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Insufficient participation of policymakers. HUBs are not collaborating in producing suitable information to be promoted. 	Policymakers and HUBs involvement are not mentioned.	-	-									

<p>Indicators</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 10,000 visits on the website and Knowledge Platform. • Impressions on newsletters, press releases and news. • Distribution of brochure/Poster/Roll up/Infographic. • Views on videos. • Followers on social networks. • 50 projects/initiatives contacted. 	<p>It is formulated only in general terms, and the different indicators are not specified in detail.</p>	<p>-</p>	<p>-</p>
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The comparison of the Logframe Matrices with the GA shows in general moderate, but in few cases significant discrepancies, omissions, and conceptual inconsistencies across several WPs.

While most WPs broadly align their **goals** with those defined in the GA, many use more general or less detailed formulations, therefore giving ground for potential misunderstandings between Coordination and WP Leads regarding the ultimate goals to achieve. The most striking examples are WP5 where the defined goals are either not clearly articulated or entirely missing and WP7 where the stated goals extend beyond the scope of the project-particularly the reference to “strategy development,” which does not appear in this form in the GA, since the main output of WP7 will be the national APs.

Regarding the **outcomes**, several WPs show gaps and misalignments with the elements defined in the GA. In WP1, only a minor confusing risk appears: the submission of official financial statements is mentioned whereas these are not required being as a lump-sum CSA. In WP2, the TWGs are not mentioned at all, despite their close connection to the HUBs and the fact that the capacity-building programme is designed for TWG Coordinators as well, not only for HUB Coordinators. In addition, cross-HUB collaboration at the macro-regional level is also not highlighted. WP3 places strong emphasis on technical detail, which may stem from its analytical nature, but the formulation diverges from the GA’s broader strategic focus. In WP5, the outcomes are formulated too generally and only partially - or in some cases not at all - reflect the areas defined in the GA. In WP6 and WP7, the content is largely consistent with the GA, but the outcomes and outputs are fully or partially reversed, which complicates readability and clarity. In addition, WP7 does not mention the alignment of APs with the SRIA, nor does it specify the development of the AP methodology framework, both of which are mentioned in the GA. Regarding WP4 and WP8, the outcomes are fully in line with the GA.

The examination of the **outputs** shows that several WPs lack, or only partially reflect, the results required by the GA. In WP2, key outputs such as the Annual Bioeconomy Conferences and the training catalogue intended also for TWG Coordinators are missing. In WP3, the listed elements - although closely related - do not constitute actual outputs but rather task lists linked to them. In WP5, many of the outputs are not aligned with the GA, and some refer to activities that do not belong to the scope of WP5. Moreover, the alignment with interministerial meetings expected in the GA are entirely absent. In WP8, the focus has shifted too strongly towards the DEC strategy, resulting in the omission of important communication outputs, such as organising science-policy dialogues or launching the mini-HUB websites. The outputs defined in WP1 and WP4 are consistent with those set out in the GA.

Across the WPs, many of the **risks** identified in the GA are either missing or only partially reflected. In WP1, the risks focus primarily on partner-related activities, omitting key elements such as external stakeholder reluctance or insufficient acceptance of the project. In WP2, the GA-defined risks concerning delays in establishing the HUBs, connectivity challenges, and

administrative or bureaucratic obstacles are not included. Although WP3 relies heavily on inputs from the HUBs, it does not mention risks related to data unavailability or challenges in organising national workshops. In WP4, while the general risk of unsuccessful pitching events is acknowledged, the specific risk of inadequate event quality is not addressed. Instead, several risks appear that are not part of the GA, such as staff capacity limitations, insufficient cooperation with HUBs, or dependencies on WP3 outputs. In WP5, the risks listed do not pertain to WP5's activities but rather to WP8, making evaluation difficult. In WP6, the only missing element is the difficulty of refreshing TWG membership. For WP7 and WP8, the identified risks are consistent with those set out in the GA.

Regarding the **indicators**, significant gaps can be observed across the WPs. In most cases, indicators are either missing entirely or are formulated so broadly that they do not meet the GA's requirements. In WP2, the stakeholder and mirror-group numbers are inaccurately defined, while in WP4 several key indicators are missing or do not match the KPI values specified in the GA. WP4 also includes indicators that are not defined in the GA - such as the innovation performance of bioeconomy sectors, communication and dissemination activities (informational email and news post), five pitching events, one multi-stakeholder workshop, the innovation ecosystem mapping report, and indicators linked to the OIC (the OIC Task Force, number of participants, and number of winners). In WP5, the GA-required indicators (e.g. expansion of the UniNet, Knowledge Platform visitor numbers) are absent, and the indicators listed are overly general, referring only to the deliverables. In WP6, the only missing element is the tracking of TWG stakeholder numbers, while in WP8 the indicators remain overly broad and insufficiently detailed, frequently providing only generic references back to the GA rather than concrete measurement criteria.

4.2 Cross-WP Comparison of the gaps and misalignments

The comparison of the Logframe Matrices reveals several cross-cutting patterns that recur consistently across the majority of WPs. These patterns indicate that the current Logframe Matrix structure only partially reflects the project logic set out in the GA and therefore require harmonisation at project level.

Several GA-defined elements - such as interministerial meetings, TWG-HUB linkages, cross-HUB collaboration, AP-SRIA alignment, the Annual Bioeconomy Conference, or expected Knowledge Platform outputs - are either only partially reflected or entirely missing in many WPs. The largest gaps appear in WP2, WP5, WP7 and WP8, while WP1, WP4 and, to some extent, WP6 show stronger alignment.

Several WPs also exhibit inconsistencies in the structure of their logical chains, with categories being mixed or misplaced. This is particularly evident in WP6 and WP7, where Outcomes and Outputs are fully or partly reversed, but similar issues appear in WP3 and WP5, where outputs

are replaced by task lists or overly generic formulations. Such category confusion significantly reduces clarity and complicates project monitoring.

The comparison further shows that key concepts - such as capacity building, stakeholder involvement, or policy dialogues - are interpreted differently across the WPs. WP2, for example, limits capacity building to HUB-level actors, although TWG Coordinators are also a target group according to the GA. WP5 assigns functions to the UniNet that go beyond its GA-defined scope, and WP7's reference to strategy development exceeds the intended remit of the WP. These variations create inconsistencies in internal logic and reduce transparency in cross-WP linkages.

Across almost all WPs, risks and indicators are either missing or insufficiently specified. GA-defined risks - such as delays in establishing HUBs, administrative or bureaucratic obstacles, or data unavailability - are not consistently included. Indicators are frequently too general or irrelevant, and only rarely aligned with the KPIs defined in the GA (notably in WP2, WP4, WP5 and WP8). This results in a fragmented monitoring framework that makes it difficult to track progress consistently across WPs and at project level.

4.3 Partner feedback and observations about the LFA

At the 2025 Annual Meeting held in Bucharest, the Coordination Team had the opportunity to present a status overview of the project to the partners, including progress across the WPs, HUBs and TWGs based on the Logframe Matrices, highlighting common patterns and areas for improvement. Following the presentation, partners were invited to provide feedback and discuss experiences. Although most of the feedback focused on improving project coordination and cross-WP collaboration and did not specifically address the LFA, several general remarks should be considered going forward such as the need for more step-by-step guidance to better complete Logframe Matrices, concerns about workload with the completion, and the importance of setting more realistic deadlines in planning the yearly activity plans. At the same time, some of the expressed needs could be substantially supported by a more effective use of the LFA itself - for example, improving the transparency of WP structures and ensuring an accessible overview of the timeline, upcoming tasks, deadlines, and responsible partners.

4.4 Project Coordination observation about the LFA

Although the WP Logframe Matrices were submitted by the planned deadline, **many WP Leaders provided incomplete or overly superficial input, despite the availability of written guidelines and online consultations**, which made the evaluation considerably more difficult. With the identified gaps and misalignments, it became clear that the WP Leads do not consult regularly with the GA. Fortunately, the number of elements missing or misaligned are generally not substantial per WP and of medium or minor importance considering overall project implementation and impact. These might be contributed to giving less attention to detail and specificities by WP Leaders when completing the matrices. The only exception is WP5

where gaps and confusion with other WPs' goals are considerable, questioning the WP5 Lead's overall understanding about its own WP activities expected to be carried out and contribution to the project as a whole.

Another recurring challenge was that **several WPs did not update their Logframe Matrices regularly**, significantly limiting the ability to monitor progress effectively. Overall, the feedback indicates that many WP Leads view the completion and updating of the Logframe Matrices as an unnecessary additional burden rather than a meaningful management tool. As a result, the **added value of the Logframe is not fully recognised**, and it is not being used to support or track their own internal processes.

Overall, developing and adapting the project's LFA proved challenging. The **terminology used in the literature is not consistent**, as the labels *Goal*, *Outcome*, and *Output* vary across sources, with *Impact* sometimes used instead of *Goal*, and *Purpose* instead of *Outcome*, even though they refer to the same underlying concepts. This inconsistency may also **have caused misunderstandings when interpreting the guidelines**, potentially contributing to incomplete or incorrect entries by WP Leads.

5 Lessons Learnt for ongoing project monitoring and evaluation

The Logframe Matrix remains a valuable tool for supporting project implementation, but it can only fulfil this function if it is regularly updated, kept current, and if WP Leaders dedicate greater effort to understanding and completing it - an aspect that may have been deprioritised amid other project responsibilities.

Below, the main lessons learnt are summarised and corresponding recommendations are outlined:

1. Standardised stakeholder identification and consistent communication channels

The stakeholder identification broadly aligns with the GA, but in several WPs certain stakeholders and communication channels that are actually involved in the work were missing. The findings indicate that standardising the stakeholder mapping and consistently documenting the communication channels are essential for maintaining internal coherence and ensuring transparent knowledge flows within the project. Therefore, during the next update process, the WP Leads' will be asked to pay attention to these gaps so that they can further improve their Logframe Matrices.

2. Enhancing WP Leaders' understanding of the LFA

The comparison of the Logframe Matrices and the GA made it clear that in several WPs key elements appear to be incomplete or inaccurate. There are frequent cases of output-outcome confusion, overly general or imprecise formulations, and the omission of KPIs or risks specified in the GA. These issues weaken the coherence of the logical chain and undermine the quality of project monitoring. The assessment also showed that many WP Leads regard the LFA

primarily as an administrative requirement rather than a management and planning tool that can genuinely support their work. This perception gap helps explain the incomplete or superficial entries and the lack of regular updates. Taken together, these findings indicate that a **deeper understanding of the LFA, as well as greater consistency across Logframe Matrices, is essential** for ensuring transparency, traceability and accountability within the project. To address these challenges, a **more detailed guideline is needed** - one that highlights the specific requirements embedded in the GA, provides clear definitions of outputs, outcomes and goals, and ensures a shared interpretation across all WPs. Equally important is the **repositioning of the Logframe Matrices' role**, therefore emphasizing even stronger the benefits of this management tool that supports planning, monitoring and strategic direction.

3. Providing simplified step-by-step guidance

Partners expressed a clear need for more transparent, step-by-step guidance and for the setting of more realistic deadlines. Going forward, it will be essential to **provide user-friendly guidelines, illustrative examples, and harmonised methodological tools**. Regular consortium meetings offer a good opportunity to discuss emerging questions and track progress. WP5 implementation needs to be paid bigger attention at regular project meetings to ensure realistic alignment with GA requirements. In addition to methodological clarity, supporting WP Leads is crucial for example through **targeted short training or quick Q&As with Coordination** that help ensure the correct and consistent use of the Logframe Matrix and at the same time gives opportunity to gather feedback from the WP Leaders. To improve content quality, it will also be important to continue regular but more focused update cycles so that project monitoring can deliver a truly comparable and coherent picture of implementation.

6 Conclusion

The implementation of the LFA within the BOOST4BIOEAST project has proven to be a valuable management and learning mechanism, ensuring coherence between strategic objectives and operational activities across all WPs. By structuring project logic through the Logframe Matrix WP Leaders have been able to plan, coordinate, and monitor their progress in a systematic and comparable way, strengthening the project's internal consistency and transparency. At the same time, it also provided Coordination with a 'panoramic view' about WP Leaders' true understanding and comprehension of their own WPs and activities expected in the project. In this way, the application of the Logframe Matrix has supported identifying gaps and misalignments between the project's expected goals, outcomes and outputs and as of 'interpreted' by each WP, therefore contributing to the development of future monitoring and evaluation measures. The process has also facilitated a common understanding among partners and encouraged a shared responsibility for achieving project results.

At the same time, the analysis highlighted several challenges that must be addressed to enhance the adaptive use of the LFA. These include the need for more regular updates and guidance by the Coordination, clearer formulation of goals, outcomes, outputs, and indicators,

and more consistent documentation of risks, assumptions, and lessons learnt by the WP Leaders. Strengthening the methodological understanding and ownership of the LFA among WP leaders will be essential for improving the precision and usability of the Logframe Matrices as living management instruments.

In summary, the LFA has provided BOOST4BIOEAST with a robust structure for aligning planning and monitoring. With continued commitment to its consistent application and improvement, the Logframe Matrix will remain an essential tool for ensuring the project's effectiveness, accountability, and contribution and will support to achieve the project's goals. The final assessment of WP Logframe Matrices including year 2 and year 3 data complemented with an analysis of the achievements and activities carried out over the entire duration of the project will be presented in *D1.5 LogFrame Methodology Second Progress Report* by M36.

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